

Commitment on Work Engagement and Employee Performance (PT. Jaya Martha Sentosa) Jakarta

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Abstract:- This research analyzes the relations between Independent and Dependent Variables, Independent Variables includes Innovative Behavior, Job Insecurity, and Organizational Commitment. Dependent Variables includes Engagement and Employee Performance, the two variables associated in this research were conducted in PT. Jaya Martha Sentosa Jakarta. This research analyzing the influence of Innovative Behavior, Job Insecurity, and Organizational Commitment directly on Employee Performance or through Work Engagement. The number of samples determined using a saturated model with total of 120 employees. In this research analysis approach using quantitative method and data collected through questionnaires, questionnaire survey was given to 120 respondents. This research used Structural Equation Model (SEM) and Smart-PLS as analysis tool on data analysis method. Results from this research showed that innovative behavior and organizational commitment significantly has positive effects on employee performance through work engagement, otherwise job insecurity has negative impacts on work engagement and it influenced employee performance.

Keywords:- Innovative behavior, Job Insecurity, Organizational Commitment, Work Engagement, Employee Performance.

I. INTRODUCTION

Human resources in a company or in organization are important and main factor for efficiency and effectiveness company or organization. The company will require human resources which has capabilities to act, think, and well-skilled, human resources are needed on dealing with the company goals and to contribute on the successful of the company itself (Sapitri, 2016). Profit-oriented companies are focused and very concerned about employee performance which for most it will affect the company's whole performance and the organization in a collective way. Basically, organizational or company performance is overall performance of employees. Therefore, the organization or company has an interest in improving employee performance to improve organizational performance. If organizational performance increases, this, of course, brings financial benefits to the company—likewise PT. Jaya Martha Sentosa is very concerned about this.

However, something worrying happened to the company's management. Based on the interview with the Director of PT. Jaya Martha Sentosa Mr. Ir. Sardomo there was a significant decrease in employee performance, the interview was conducted by the author at the end of March 2021 at the company office. Results from interview said, there was a declining in employee performance from 2018. This statement is supported by the employee performance appraisal documents in 2018 and 2019, where from the results of the performance appraisal, there is a significant decrease.

No	Name	Position	Appraisal Job Insecurity Year 2018	Appraisal Job Insecurity Year 2019	(%)
1	X	Project Manager	75	84	5,70%
2	B	Site Manager	80	85	3%
3	C	Purchasing	74	81	4,50%
4	D	Staff finance	76	82	3,80%
5	E	Engineering	76	80	2,60%
6	F	Logistik	78	80	1,30%
7	G	Drafter	74	82	5,10%
8	H	Staff Admin	68	75	4,90%
9	I	Supervisor	70	74	2,80%
10	J	Asisten Supervisor	72	78	4%
11	K	Surveyor	76	80	2,60%
12	L	Security	78	84	3,70%

Table 1: Appraisal Performance Employee PT. Jaya Martha Sentosa

Sources of processed data (2021)

The data listed in the table above shows that there is a decrease in the employee performance of PT. Jaya Martha Sentosa has almost all levels of positions that exist in individuals who occupy various positions. From the interview, the company leadership are worried about the data. The exemplary and increment of employee performance or the increasing and decreasing of employee performance definitely affecting the company's performance (Saputro & Nawangsari, 2021). The important of employee performance

in an organization or in a company is because it can affect organizational performance (Sinaga & Nawangsari, 2019). The employee performance and organizational performance are associated and related. The success or the achievement of company's goal are within and cannot separated from the resources mostly human resources or employee who worked for the company. Human resources or employees have an active role as main actor to achieve the company's goals (Amrainy & Nawangsari, 2021).

No	Name	Position	Appraisal Job Insecurity Year 2018	Appraisal Job Insecurity Year 2019	(%)
1	X	Project Manager	80	74	3,90%
2	B	Site Manager	85	74	7%
3	C	Purchasing	74	65	6,50%
4	D	Staff finance	73	62	8,10%
5	E	Engineering	71	60	8,40%
6	F	Logistik	76	68	5,60%
7	G	Drafter	85	68	11,10%
8	H	Staff Admin	80	76	2,60%
9	I	Supervisor	84	68	10,50%
10	J	Asisten Supervisor	80	74	4%
11	K	Surveyor	80	65	10,30%
12	L	Security	74	72	1,40%

Tabel 2: Appraisal Work Engagement PT. Jaya Martha Sent

Sources of uuuu processed data (2021)

The data listed in the table above shows that there is a decrease in Work Engagement at PT. Jaya Martha Sentosa has almost all levels of positions that exist in individuals who occupy various positions. This is, of course, very worrying

company leadership. We all know that work engagement is good and bad; increasing and decreasing will definitely have an impact on company performance.

No	Name	Position	Appraisal Job Insecurity Year 2018	Appraisal Job Insecurity Year 2019	(%)
1	X	Project Manager	82	72	6,50%
2	B	Site Manager	80	72	5%
3	C	Purchasing	75	63	9,00%
4	D	Staff finance	70	64	10,40%
5	E	Engineering	74	65	6,50%
6	F	Logistik	78	66	8,30%
7	G	Drafter	80	75	3,20%
8	H	Staff Admin	82	75	4,50%
9	I	Supervisor	82	75	4,50%
10	J	Asisten Supervisor	83	76	4%
11	K	Surveyor	80	72	5,30%
12	L	Security	70	66	4,40%

Tabel 3: Appraisal Innovative Behavior PT. Jaya Martha Sentosa

Sources of processed data (2021)

The data are listed in Table 3 indicate that a decline in Innovative Behavior PT. Jaya Martha Sentosa has almost all levels of positions that exist in individuals who occupy various positions. This is, of course, very worrying

company leadership. We all know that Innovative Behavior is good and bad, up and down, definitely has an impact on the company's performance.

No	Name	Position	Appraisal Job Insecurity Year 2018	Appraisal Job Insecurity Year 2019	(%)
1	X	Project Manager	86	74	12,00%
2	B	Site Manager	92	78	8%
3	C	Purchasing	74	66	5,70%
4	D	Staff finance	73	65	5,80%
5	E	Engineering	68	62	3,80%
6	F	Logistik	73	67	4,30%
7	G	Drafter	92	76	9,50%
8	H	Staff Admin	75	71	2,70%
9	I	Supervisor	93	75	10,70%
10	J	Asisten Supervisor	76	68	6%
11	K	Surveyor	93	75	10,70%
12	L	Security	74	72	1,40%

Tabel 4: Appraisal Job Insecurity PT. Jaya Martha Sentosa

Sources of processed data (2021)

The data listed in Table 4 shows that there is a decrease in Job Insecurity at PT. Jaya Martha Sentosa has almost all levels of positions that exist in individuals who occupy various positions. The company leadership are worried about

the data. Job Insecurity has negative and positive impact on the company performance either it will decrease or increase the company's performance.

No	Name	Position	Appraisal Job Insecurity Year 2018	Appraisal Job Insecurity Year 2019	(%)
1	X	Project Manager	78	74	2,60%
2	B	Site Manager	82	76	4%
3	C	Purchasing	74	70	2,80%
4	D	Staff finance	80	77	1,90%
5	E	Engineering	76	72	2,70%
6	F	Logistik	79	85	3,70%
7	G	Drafter	76	83	4,40%
8	H	Staff Admin	70	77	4,80%
9	I	Supervisor	72	76	2,70%
10	J	Asisten Supervisor	74	79	3%
11	K	Surveyor	75	81	3,80%
12	L	Security	82	88	3,50%

Tabel 5: Appraisal Organizational Commitment PT. Jaya Martha Sentosa

Sources of processed data (2021)

Table 5 From the data listed in the table above shows that there is a decrease in the Organizational Commitment of PT. Jaya Martha Sentosa has almost all levels of positions that exist in individuals who occupy various positions. This is, of course, very worrying company leadership. Organizational commitment itself can generally be defined as employee loyalty and attachment to the organization where they work (Lestari, 2020). According to Porter in Lestari and Nawangsari, organizational commitment has three

psychological factors, namely identification, involvement, and loyalty (Lestari & Nawangsari Lenny C, 2019). As known that good and bad Organizational Commitment, it definitely will increase and decrease and affecting the company's performance; this is also reflected in the annual gross income from 2018 to 2020, there is a decrease in gross income achieved by the company, this is strengthened by data and table 6.

No	Year	Gross Income	Year	Gross Income	Decrease
1	2018	Rp. 35.750.269.373	2019	Rp. 31.613.410.292	13%
2	2019	Rp. 31.613.410.292	2020	Rp. 17.221.890.099	45,52%

Table 6: Gross income per year

Table 6 illustrates or reinforces that the decline in employee performance impacting the company's gross income, which is also declining. This is a strong signal that there is a problem with Employee Performance at PT. Jaya Martha Sentosa. The problems that happened in company influenced by several factors that make Employee Performance decline, including Work Engagement. Work engagement is a psychological component that is not physical in nature or in other words. It is not necessarily an employee who will have a work attachment even though the employee has worked for a long time in a company. Work engagement is a concept that can shows or reflect that an individual employee has a strong passion, dedication, and focus on working and contributing for the company. Individuals who usually carry out tasks according to their responsibilities may have low work engagement (Wulandari & Ratnaningsih, 2017)

II. THEORETICAL REVIEW

Wibowo (2012) defined performance as a process of work progress and as a result achieved by work (Wibowo & Mahfud, 2012). The work result itself show employee performance. Sutedjo & Mangkunegara(2013) stated that employee performance is a work result that assessed in terms of quality and quantity that has been successfully attained by an employee in accomplishing their work in compliance with the tasks and responsibilities that has been gained(Sutedjo & Mangkunegara, 2013). From this statement, employee performance can be understood as real behaviour of an

employee to achieve the result of duties that will generated in compliance with the roles, tasks, responsibilities given (Nawangsari, 2019). From several literature reviews and existing theories, the authors refer to the dimensions and indicators of employee performance based on Mangkunegara (2013) said that performance was influenced by three main key factors or dimensions, such as; (1) individual factor or dimension, it can be said as individual attributes; (2) psychological factor or dimension, also can be said as work effort; (3) organizational factor or dimension, can be said as organizational support (Mangkunegara, 2015).

Schaufeli et al. (2002) explained work engagement as a positivity and a form of fulfilment of work which is characterized as the centre of mind(Wilmar B. Schaufeli et al., 2002).As previous statement said, work engagement can defined as a centre of positive mind and thought and motivation, associated and characterized by dedication, vigor or passion, and absorption. According to Kahn, work engagement is conceptualized as company's employee or organizational members who bear the work role, work load, and express their own self in physical, cognitive, and emotional way during work. Which means that work is everything for their life, it can be summarized that work engagement is an indication that work can be done without coercion or force, both physically and psychologically and the employee work with enthusiasm and satisfaction during work (Mujiasih & Ratnaningsih, 2011).

Prayudhayanti (2014) defined innovative behaviour as an individual capability to evolve and changing the way of work and managing the way to work, in adapting and to form new practices or techniques, and procedures, even work environment, in accomplishing tasks (Prayudhayanti, 2014). Marcellinus et al. (2014) said innovative behaviour is individual’s overall behaviour that refers to emergence, introduction, and implementation of new things that will beneficial and profitable for the company or organization at all levels (Marcellinus et al., 2014). According to the statement, new things that profitable and beneficial are development of ideas or technology in new products and changes in administrative procedures aimed at improving working relations. In addition, innovative behaviour is an important and main key factor that determined the success of organization or company ability to maintain a competitive advantage (Najib & Nawangsari, 2021).

Job insecurity according to Greenhalgh and Rosenblatt (1984) is an inability to maintain the continuation of work because of the threat of the situation from a job (Greenhalgh & Rosenblatt, 1984). Sverke & Hellgren (2014) said job insecurity is an insecure feeling from a person that the person feels about the sustainability of the work and main aspect associated with the job itself. Furthermore, Sverke & Hellgren (2014) utter job insecurity as employee’s subjective view on situation or event that threaten their job position in the company their work for (de Cuyper et al., 2014).

The sustainability, continuation, achievement, and successful company or organization are influenced by work engagement and employee performance. According to the

statement, it makes the company or organizational institution to continue striving and improving employee performance in achieving company’s goals with maximum results. In addition, company’s or organization’s cultures can also improve performance in long term. Organization’s culture or corporate’s cultures relatively durable unit of values and norms that organizational members or employees, implement it as norms of behaviour in dealing and solving company problems (Nur et al., 2019). This research shows independent variables are; Innovative Behaviour; Job Insecurity; and Organizational Commitment; which have influence on dependent variables that are; Employee Performance; Work Engagement.

III. METHODS

A. Type of Research Design

This research used quantitative descriptive analysis, assisted by the SmartPLS 3.0 software. The Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) method was used by researchers in this study. Noor (2011) said The Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) is an analytical technique which can enable sample examination as relations chain which simultaneously build between one or various independent variables to one or various dependent variables (Abdullahhasan et al., 2019).

B. Research Approach

Quantitative research is a research approach that uses numbering, starting from collecting data, interpreting data, and displaying results. Quantitative data in this research were obtained or collected through questionnaires.

Fig. 1: Research Framework

Source: Primary Data, 2020

- X_1 = Innovative Behavior
- X_2 = Job Insecurity
- X_3 = Organizational Commitment
- Z = Work Engagement (Intervening)
- Y = Employee Performance

IV. RESEARCH RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

• Data Analysis Results

Reliability is reliableness examination which aims to discover the accuracy of measurement from the variables

to show the reliableness and trust ability of the research. Primadana Putra (2014) explained that questionnaire method can be proven reliable or trusted if the correspondent’s answers toward the questions are stable and consistent frequently (Primadana Putra, 2014). On the beginning of first step, construction can be proved reliable and trustworthy if the construct has a composition of reality above value 0.70 (Ghozali & Fuad, 2014). It can be shown that, the outcome of the outer model of composite reliability is:

Variable	Composite Reliability	Condition	Cronbach's Alpha	Condition	Description
Innovative Behavior(X1)	0.721	> 0.7	0.746	> 0.6	Reliable
Job Insecurity (X2)	0.858	> 0.7	0.811	> 0.6	Reliable
Organizational Commitment (X3)	0.897	> 0.7	0.857	> 0.6	Reliable
Work Engagement (Y1)	0.868	> 0.7	0.831	> 0.6	Reliable
Employee Performance (Y2)	0.905	> 0.7	0.887	> 0.6	Reliable

Table 7: Composite Reliability Value of the Research Model

Table 7 Shows a table of composite or construct reliability values, according to research analysis the authors have explained and used in this research. Based on the table, it can be seen that each of the variables have construct reliability values, the dependent and independent variables are more than or above 0.7. As it can be seen, Innovative Behavior or variable X1 has the lowest value, with 0.721. Otherwise, variable Employee Performance or Y2 has the highest value, with 0.905. It can be summarized that this research analysis has reached the value of composite or construct reliability. In comparison, the value of Cronbach's alpha according to the table appeared that every variable has Cronbach's alpha value because all the variables above and more than 0.6. As previously, variable of Innovative Behavior or X1 has the lowest value, with 0.746 and the highest value still from variable of Employee Performance or Y2 with 0.887. In conclusion, the results from the table show that research model has reached the value of Cronbach's

alpha and has reached the criteria of Composite Reliability. From the research model it shows that the reliability of this analysis is reliable and trusted in measuring variable instrument.

This research Inner model evaluation using the Coefficient of Determination. To measure how far the model's ability to explain the variance of the dependent variable is the aim using the Coefficient of Determination. The value of the coefficient of determination is between 0 and 1. The value of the coefficient of determination (R^2) is close to the value of 1. The value of R^2 explains how much the independent variable hypothesized in the equation is able to explain the dependent variable. Chin (Chin, 1998) in Yamin & Kurniawan (Yamin & Kurniawan, 2011) explains the criteria for limiting the value of R^2 in three classifications, namely the value of $R^2 = 0.67, 0.33, \text{ and } 0.19$ as substantial, moderate, and weak.

Construct	R Square	R Square Adjusted
Work Engagement (Y1)	0.833	0.822
Employee Performance (Y2)	0.950	0.920

Table 8: Value of R Square (R^2) of the Research Model

As seen in Table 8, the relationship between constructs based on the Adjusted R-square value can be explained that the Work Engagement variable (Y1) is 0.822, this shows that 82.2% of the Work Engagement variable (Y1) can be influenced by the Innovative Behavior variable (X1), Job Insecurity (X2), and Organizational Commitment (X3), while the remaining 17.8% is influenced by other variables outside the research. While the relationship between constructs based on the Adjusted R-square value can be explained that the

Employee Performance variable (Y2) is 0.920, this shows that 92.0% of the Employee Performance variable (Y2) can be influenced by the Innovative Behavior variable (X1), Job Insecurity (X2), Organizational Commitment (X3), and Work Engagement variables (Y1), while the remaining 8.0% is influenced by other variables outside the research.

The results of hypothesis testing using Smart PLS 3.0 software can be seen in Table 9 as follows:

Relationship between Constructs	Original Sample (O)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values	Description
Direct Influence				
Innovative Behavior -> Work Engagement	0.643	6.394	0.000	Significant Positive Influence
Innovative Behavior -> Employee Performance	0.728	7.446	0.000	Significant Positive Influence
Job Insecurity -> Work Engagement	-0.445	3.463	0.001	Significant Positive Influence
Job Insecurity -> Employee Performance	-0.261	2.714	0.007	Significant Positive Influence
Organizational Commitment -> Work Engagement	0.666	5.505	0.000	Significant Positive Influence
Organizational Commitment -> Employee Performance	0.283	2.133	0.033	Significant Positive Influence
Work Engagement -> Employee Performance	0.593	5.096	0.000	Significant Positive Influence
Indirect Influence				
Innovative Behavior -> Work Engagement-> Employee Performance	0.033	0.149	0.882	Not Mediation
Job Insecurity -> Work Engagement-> Employee Performance	-0.282	0.905	0.366	Not Mediation
Organizational Commitment -> Work Engagement-> Employee Performance	0.095	0.513	0.608	Not Mediation

Relationship between Constructs	Original Sample (O)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values	Description
Employee Performance				

Table 9: Path Coefficient Value, t-Statistics, dan P-Values

Source: hypothesis testing using Smart PLS 3.0

- There is a positive and significant Influence of Innovative Behavior (X1) on Work Engagement (Y1)
Based on table 4.24, it is known that the value of t statistics is 6.394, which is greater than the value of t table = 1.98, and the value of P-Values = 0.000 which is smaller than $\pm = 0.05$. The coefficient value is positive, which is 0.643, meaning that the Innovative Behavior variable (X1) has a positive effect on the Work Engagement variable (Y1) by 64.3%. Thus the hypothesis H1 in this study which states that "Innovative Behavior (X1) has a positive and significant effect on Work Engagement (Y1)" is accepted.
- There is a negative and significant influence of Job Insecurity (X2) on Work Engagement (Y1)
Based on table 4.24, it is known that the value of t statistics is 3.463, which is greater than the value of t table = 1.98, and the value of P-Values = 0.001 which is smaller than $\pm = 0.05$. The coefficient value is negative, which is -0.445, meaning that the Job Insecurity variable (X2) has a negative effect on the Work Engagement variable (Y1) by 44.5%. Thus the hypothesis H2 in this study which states that "Job Insecurity (X2) has a negative and significant effect on Work Engagement (Y1)," is accepted.
- There is a positive and significant influence of Organizational Commitment (X3) on Work Engagement (Y1)
Based on table 4.24, it is known that the value of t statistics is 5.505, which is greater than the value of t table = 1.98, and the value of P-Values = 0.000, which is smaller than $\pm = 0.05$. The coefficient value is positive, which is 0.666, meaning that the Organizational Commitment (X3) variable has a positive effect on the Work Engagement variable (Y1) by 66.6%. Thus the hypothesis H3 in this study which states that "Organizational Commitment (X3) has a positive and significant effect on Work Engagement (Y1)" is accepted.
- There is a positive and significant influence of Work Engagement (Y1) on Employee Performance (Y2)
Based on table 4.24, it is known that the value of t statistics is 5.096, which is greater than the value of t table = 1.98, and the value of P-Values = 0.000, which is smaller than $\pm = 0.05$. The coefficient value is positive, which is 0.593, meaning that the Work Engagement variable (Y1) has a positive effect on the Employee Performance (Y2) variable of 59.3%. Thus the H4 hypothesis in this study which states that "Work Engagement (Y1) has a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance (Y2)" is accepted.
- There is a positive and significant influence of Innovative Behavior (X1) on Employee Performance (Y2)
Based on table 4.24, it is known that the value of t statistics is 7.446, which is greater than the value of t table = 1.98, and the value of P-Values = 0.000, which is smaller than $\pm = 0.05$. The coefficient value is positive, which is 0.728, meaning that the Innovative Behavior variable (X1) has a positive effect on the Employee Performance variable (Y2)

by 72.8%. Thus the hypothesis H5 in this study which states that "Innovative Behavior (X1) has a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance (Y2)," is accepted.

- There is a negative and significant effect of Job Insecurity (X2) on Employee Performance (Y2)
Based on table 4.24, it is known that the t statistics value is 2.714, which is greater than the t table value = 1.98, and the P-Values = 0.007, which is smaller than $\pm = 0.05$. The coefficient value is negative, which is -0.261, meaning that the Job Insecurity variable (X2) has a negative effect on the Employee Performance variable (Y2) by 26.1%. Thus the hypothesis H6 in this study which states that "Job Insecurity (X2) has a negative and significant effect on Employee Performance (Y2)," is accepted.
- There is a positive and significant influence of Organizational Commitment (X3) on Employee Performance (Y2)
Based on table 4.24, it is known that the t statistics value is 2.133, which is greater than the t table value = 1.98, and the P-Values = 0.033, which is smaller than $\pm = 0.05$. The coefficient value is positive, which is 0.283, meaning that the Organizational Commitment (X3) variable has a positive effect on the Employee Performance (Y2) variable by 28.3%. Thus the hypothesis H7 in this study which states that "Organizational Commitment (X3) has a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance (Y2)," is accepted.
- There is a positive and significant influence of Innovative Behavior (X1) on Employee Performance (Y2) through the Work Engagement variable (Y1)
Based on table 4.24, it is known that the t-statistics value of the Innovative Behavior variable is 0.149, which is smaller than the t-table value = 1.98, and the P-Values = 0.882, which is greater than $\pm = 0.05$. The coefficient value is positive, which is 0.033, meaning that the Innovative Behavior variable (X1) has a positive effect on the Employee Performance variable (Y2) through Work Engagement (Y1) by 3.3%. Thus the hypothesis H8 in this study which states that "Innovative Behavior (X1) has a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance (Y2) through the Work Engagement variable (Y1)," is rejected.
- There is a negative and significant influence of Job Insecurity (X2) on Employee Performance (Y2) through the Work Engagement variable (Y1)
Based on table 4.24, it is known that the t statistics value of the Job Insecurity variable is 0.905, which is smaller than the t table value = 1.98, and the P-Values = 0.366, which is greater than $\pm = 0.05$. The coefficient value is negative, which is -0.282, meaning that the Job Insecurity variable (X2) has a negative effect on the Employee Performance (Y2) variable through Work Engagement (Y1) by 28.2%. Thus the hypothesis H9 in this study which states that "Job

Insecurity (X2) has a negative and significant effect on Employee Performance (Y2) through the Work Engagement variable (Y1)," is rejected.

- There is a positive and significant influence of Organizational Commitment (X3) on Employee Performance (Y2) through the Work Engagement variable (Y1)

Based on table 4.24, it is known that the value of t statistics for the Organizational Commitment variable is 0.513, which is smaller than the value of t table = 1.98, and the P-Values = 0.608, which is greater than $\pm = 0.05$. The coefficient value is positive, which is 0.095, meaning that the Organizational Commitment (X3) variable has a positive effect on the Employee Performance variable (Y2) through Work Engagement (Y1) by 9.5%. Thus the hypothesis H10 in this study which states that "Organizational Commitment (X3) has a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance (Y2) through the Work Engagement variable (Y1)," is rejected.

V. CONCLUSION

From result and discussion, can be summarized that data analysis using proof of the hypothesis from the problem explained and discussed on Chapter 4. Can be summarized as follows:

- Innovative behavior influenced Work Engagement, with the important precursor role of creativity and innovation in the workplace. Emotional and positive states such as a sense of meaning and active work are related to creativity. The higher pressure to compete can encourage employees to work better and have a positive effect on the emergence of innovative behavior. These positive conditions encourage employees to work harder because of their appreciation for their work. This state of work engagement is closely related to the effects that can encourage innovative behavior.
- Job Insecurity affects Work Engagement; when employees do not feel compelled to carry out the demands of their work, they will tend to give more than what their job demands. This is an indication that the individual is engaged with his job.
- Company or organizational commitment effecting Work Engagement, with self-determination theory encouraging individuals to take the desired actions that come from within so that they are able to identify and achieve goals based on the individual's knowledge and assessment of himself. In this case, the goals of the organization are able to become a benchmark for individuals in developing their potential so that they are able to be engaged in their organization.
- Innovative behavior affects Employee Performance, the higher the innovative behavior of an employee is shown by finding new opportunities in serving consumers, having new ideas in solving problems, finding new ways of working, new ways to improve product quality, then being able to improve their performance. The interaction between superiors and employees who have a positive relationship with their boss is more likely to exhibit innovative work behavior and is able to provide confidence that their innovative behavior will result in improved performance.

- Job Insecurity affects the Employee Performance, employees who feel concerned will be the certainty of its work so as not optimal in completing responsibilities he replied. When an employee there is a stage that exceeds the level of insecurity which could be bear, then the response that generated these employees will react negatively in the form of, among others, lack of quality performance, increased absenteeism or negligence, lack of participation while working, and low self-motivation. So, the greater the job insecurity felt by the employee, the lower the performance resulting from the employee, and vice versa.
- Organizational or company commitment effecting Employee Performance; high commitment on organization or company, can be needed in an organization because the creation of high commitment will affect a professional work situation. The importance of building affective commitment, normative commitment, and ongoing commitment as dimensions of organizational commitment to employees of PT. Jaya Martha Sentosa because it will improve employee performance.
- Work Engagement influenced Employee Performance; employee involvement indicates results in increasing employee performance, which leads to organizational employee performance on good work engagement for employees of PT. Jaya Martha Sentosa can increase a close relationship with the company that makes the employee (without being compelled) make an optimal contribution to the company. Work engagement can create success for the company through improving employee performance. On the other hand, the result of low employee engagement not only has an impact on performance but also increases turnover intention, decreases customer service satisfaction, and increases absenteeism.
- Innovative behavior doesn't effecting Employee Performance beyond or by way of variable Work Engagement. In the results of this study, it was found that the results of hypothesis testing that innovative behavior had no effect on employee performance through work engagement variables, this can be seen from the results of hypothesis testing the value of t statistics for innovative behavior variables is 0.149 which is smaller than the value of t table = 1.98, and the value of P-Values = 0.882 which is greater than $\pm = 0.05$.
- Job Insecurity doesn't effecting Employee Performance through the Work Engagement variable. In the results of this study, it was found that the hypothesis test results that job insecurity has no effect on employee performance through the work engagement variable, this can be seen from the results of hypothesis testing the value of t statistics for the job insecurity variable is 0.905 which is smaller than the value of t table = 1.98, and the value of P-Values = 0.366 which is greater than $\alpha = 0,05$.
- Company or Organizational commitment doesn't effecting Employee Performance through the Work Engagement variable. In the results of this study, it was found that the results of hypothesis testing that Organizational Commitment had no effect on Employee Performance through the Work Engagement variable, this can be seen from the results of hypothesis testing, the t statistics value of the Organizational Commitment variable is 0.513 which

is smaller than the value of t table = 1.98, and the value of P -values = 0.608 greater than $\hat{I} \pm = 0.05$.

VI. SUGGESTIONS

Innovative behavior has a significant positive effect on Employee Performance, in this case the company must stimulate innovative behavior from within the company, for example holding competitions for innovative initiators, carrying out trainings related to innovativeness, and managers must provide examples of innovative behavior to the employees under them. . The managerial implementation that can be carried out by the company is by carrying out activities that can improve communication between employees, one of which is conducting team building gatherings that involve all departments to train fair play, critical thinking, teamwork and communication between departments.

The researcher suggests to minimize the influence of the company's job insecurity by clarifying the organizational structure and job description of each individual who occupies all positions or positions within the organization so that role ambiguity can be minimized. There should be no concurrent positions, where multiple positions will cause new problems, namely unclear roles and responsibilities and unprofessional and not optimal in carrying out work. The managerial implementation that can be done is to conduct regular Focus Group Discussions (FGD) with employees once a year to discuss progress targets, goals, desired upskills and job satisfaction in accordance with the employee's skills.

Organizational Commitment has a significant positive effect on the Employee Performance variable. Managerial implementations that can be applied include loyal employees, incentives are not the main thing to improve employee performance, but employee confidence in the company itself. Companies can give rewards to employees who contribute or hold employee awards to give appreciation to loyal employees.

Continuance Commitment, researchers suggest that companies hold trainings that are official bonds with binding provisions between the company and employees, if employees want to resign they will consider the losses that will be borne. With official ties, the company can also get qualified employees with a comparable investment value. Managerial implementation that can be done is by providing assistance for studies or support programs within official bonds so that they can produce human resources who have good competencies.

Work engagement, based on the correlation table between dimensions which illustrates that the Work Engagement variable has a significant positive effect on Employee Performance on the Job Resources Dimension, the researcher suggests that the Company fix the physical, social and psychological aspects so that it has a better or greater impact on Employee Performance.

Concretely for the physical, the company must organize the company environment to be more comfortable, for the social the company must stimulate social activities within the

company environment, as well as the psychological aspect, the managerial implementation of the company must maintain psychology within reasonable limits by providing counseling clinics. In this counseling, every employee who has a problem can consult the problems they face so that they do not interfere with work so that it does not have a negative impact on Employee Performance.

Employee performance, it is very important for the management of research subjects to continue to maintain engagement with employees, so that employees continue to be motivated to improve their performance. Efforts that can be made include, among others, fostering and maintaining harmonious relations between leaders and employees, providing training or workshops, as well as hospitality or gatherings at least once a month. The managerial implementation that can be done by the company is by placing employees in the appropriate department so that the employee can innovate and contribute well, the placement of human resources can be done by holding KPI tests or a fair competition to hone skills and also improve functional positions in the company.

For further research, it is possible to develop a research model by developing a larger and more varied population and sample with a wider coverage area, so that it becomes useful input for the company, as well as our scientific insight in the field of management science, such as using Theory Planned Behavior or researching variables outside This research includes motivation, career development, transformational leadership, and others.

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